

Iroooooo14 - Itserr

Quality Assessment Plan (QAP)

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Mission 4 – Component 2 under the project ITSERR Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE

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Change history

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01.00	22/12/2022	FINAL	Revised by the Board
01.01	01/04/2023	FINAL	Changes in staff names

Distribution List

Name	Company	Role
ITSERR Board Members	All ITSERR partners	

This document is available in the ITSERR WP Management document repository at:
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1 Document overview

1.1 Objectives

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR¹) for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

This document is the Quality Assessment Plan (QAP) for the Grant and represents the reference document by which ITSERR demonstrates that it:

- has selected the most appropriate WP organisations, techniques, resources, and tools to cope with the above,
- has defined the deliverables, quality assurance, and approval responsibilities and processes and defined the extent and format of checks and reviews,

¹ ITSERR is a consortium composed of National Research Council (CNR), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), Università di Napoli L'Orientale (UNIOR), University of Palermo (UNIPA) and Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO).

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- has identified the major risks and the corresponding preventive actions.

The major purposes of this QAP are:

- the provisions for risk management;
- a description of the effective performance indicators;
- the definition of the procedures to make an efficient use of external feedbacks to ensure the continuous improvement of the project;
- an analysis of the instrument to evaluate the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination efficacy;
- an effective strategy to deal with gender and ethics issues.

1.2 Scope

This Quality Assessment Plan covers exclusively the GA organisational bodies:

ITSERR

as defined in the Grant Agreement IR00000014 - ITSERR (see applicable document [A2]).

This QAP is to be applied by each staff employed on the WP and to all work performed within it. It is a binding document being part of the contractual documents. In case of misinterpretation or conflicts, the Grant Agreement Contract and its annexes have precedence over this document.

1.3 Applicable documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[A1]	09/08/2022	ATTO D'OBBLIGO CONNESSO ALL'ACCETTAZIONE DEL FINANZIAMENTO CONCESSO PER IL PROGETTO "ITSERR - Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE" - CUP B53C22001770006
[A2]		
[A3]		
[A4]		
[A5]		
[A6]		

All documents mentioned in this list are available in the Document Repository, section "Applicable Documents".

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1.4 Reference documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[R1]	28/11/2022	Detailed Organisational Plan

1.5 Glossary

A glossary of terms and acronyms used in this document is included in section 8.

1.6 Acronyms

A list of acronyms frequently used in this document.

Term	Definition
CO	Collaborator of a PI (Principal Investigator)
FO	Financial Officer
GA	Grant Agreement
IAB	International Advisory Board
IB	ITSERR Board
IB members	General Assembly
IM	Infrastructure Manager
ITSERR	Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca
OU	Organisational Unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PI	Principal Investigator
PLA	Performance Level Agreement
PRC	Peer Review Committee
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SSF	Stakeholders Strategic Forum

TNA

Trans-National Access

VA

Virtual Access

2 Presentation of the Grant Agreement

2.1 Definition of the objectives

ITSERR is based on the postulate that the Humanities can offer superdiverse datasets whose complexity challenges technologies and ICT scholars. Therefore, the project aims at transforming the scientific community of Religious Studies from being a mere actor in the implementation of established technologies to the driver of a new match with the new assets of Artificial Intelligence/Big Data/HPC.

The project is implemented to:

- strengthen the RESILIENCE RI in its preparatory phase, through its national institutional dimension, scientific positioning, technical development and public perception;
- support excellence by putting the more qualified scholars and researchers in Religious Studies and ICT at the service of the excellence in research in Religious Studies, producing disruptive innovation for the domain;
- advance efficiency with the improvement of the accessibility to data, facilities and experts belonging to the national context and promoting data FAIRness;
- expand the RI national network of researchers, users and stakeholders, and be able to translate the national experience on other national contexts and at the European level;
- enhance operativity by offering new services and tools that are ready to be accessed by the end of the project and can thus rapidly enable new research scenarios and
- attract scholarship, research and industry to leverage the Italian scientific community of Religious Studies towards a more innovation-oriented research methodology.

2.2 ITSERR partners Organisational Units (OU)

OU	Accr.	Description
OU1	CNR-ISTI	Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione A. Faedo, Via Moruzzi 1, 56124, Pisa
OU2	UNIMORE-DESU	Dipartimento di Educazione e Scienze Umane
OU3	UNIMORE-DIEF	Dipartimento di Ingegneria "Enzo Ferrari"
OU4	UNIOR-DAAM	Dipartimento Asia Africa e Mediterraneo, Piazza San Domenico Maggiore 12, 80133 Napoli
OU5	UNIPA-DCS	Dipartimento Culture e Società, Viale delle Scienze ed.15, 98128, Palermo
OU6	UNIPA-DMI	Dipartimento di Matematica e Informatica, via Archirafi 34, 90123 Palermo

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OU7	UNIPA-DI	Dipartimento di Ingegneria, Viale delle Scienze, ed. 8, 90128 Palermo
OU8	UNIPA-IUS	Dipartimento di Giurisprudenza
OU9	UNIPA-ARCH	Dipartimento di Architettura
OU10	UNITO-DSS	Dipartimento di Studi Storici, Via Sant'Ottavio 20, 10124, Torino

2.3 Global contract phasing

The MUR imposes a certain phasing related to the reporting obligations of the ITSERR partners.

“Rendicontazione di intervento: Rendicontazione bimestrale al Servizio centrale per il PNRR da parte della funzione di rendicontazione e controllo dell’Amministrazione centrale titolare di intervento. Tale attività può ricomprendere la rendicontazione delle spese sostenute dai soggetti attuatori e/o la rendicontazione del conseguimento dei milestone e target associati agli interventi di competenza;”

Aside this, the partners have decided to split the execution of the GA in 12 distinct Work Packages (WP). These are:

Table 1 : List of Work Packages

WP	WP Title	Leader	Start month	End month
WP1	Project Management + Impact	OU1	1	30
WP2	RESILIENCE Data Centre Services	OU5	2	29
WP3	T-ReS	OU2	2	29
WP4	DamSym	OU5	2	29
WP5	DIGITAL MAKTABA	OU5	2	29
WP6	YASMINE	OU5	2	29
WP7	REVER	OU2	2	29
WP8	uBIQUity	OU5	2	29
WP9	Taurus	OU10	2	29
WP10	ReTINA	OU4	2	29
WP11	TNA	OU5	2	29
WP12	Data Management Services	OU5	2	29

2.4 Materials and Services supplied by the MUR

To execute and respect the procedures created by MUR under PNRR, they have provided to the ITSERR community the following material:

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- The Grant Agreement
- REGIS, the project portal of MUR
- Templates for technical and financial reporting

3 Management Processes

3.1 Document Management

3.1.1 Purpose

The purpose of the Document Management Process is to:

- Define roles and responsibilities related to document management
- Define the process and standards for document preparation, review, and approval
- Define the methods for document change control and version control
- Define the approach to document storage, backup, and retention

It presents the document handling policy, which aims to ensure that:

- All documents that are part of the documentation baseline are managed and controlled according to documented and supported processes and tools.
- All baseline documents are made available to all personnel involved in the WP at the appropriate time, with appropriate access.

3.1.2 Scope

The Document Management Process is applicable to all documents produced by all services covered by the Grant.

3.1.3 Process Description

The Document Management Process is applicable to the documents relevant to the following services:

- Management bodies
- Advisory bodies
- Work Package execution

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 3.1.4 Process Diagram

Figure 1: Document Management process

Figure 2: Document Production

3.1.5 Roles and Responsibilities

Roles	Party	Description
PMO	ITSERR	<p>The PMO is responsible for establishing the proper Document Management follow-up and for guaranteeing the consistency of the document deliverables for MUR.</p> <p>The PMO ensures that all the documents provided by the authors always meet the quality requirements of the client for MUR deliverables</p>
Quality Reviewer	ITSERR	The PMO takes on board the Quality Review to ensure that all the documents provided by the authors meet the MUR quality requirements
Author	ITSERR	A document author is a person with technical knowledge to define the contents of documents. He is the owner and the manager of the produced document.
Reviewer	ITSERR	<p>Each body and WP team can nominate a (set of) Reviewers to ensure that all the documents provided by the authors meet the specific requirements (ie scientific, IT, legal, etc).</p> <p>A document reviewer's responsibilities vary somewhat depending upon the type of review being conducted. There are both technical and language reviews. Technical reviewers are responsible for judging a document's technical accuracy. Language reviewers are responsible for proofreading documentation for proper spelling, grammar, and continuity.</p>
Approver(s)	ITSERR, MUR	People involved in the document approval process. First the document is approved internally to ITSERR before its submission to MUR. The later realises another review/approval process to accept ITSERR deliverable.

Table 2 : Document Management Process – List of roles

3.1.5.1 Author

Document authors are individuals with the scientific/technical/managerial knowledge to define the contents of documents. If several authors contribute to a single document, one author is identified as the main author to ensure good communication and coordination. This person's document-handling responsibilities are:

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- To prepare the structure and contents of documents.
- To submit the documents for review at the appropriate level, and verify subsequent updates resulting there from.
- To ensure consistency between document contents and current baseline.

The authors are also involved with the layout and administrative handling of the documents. Their document-handling responsibilities are:

- To lay out documents in accordance with the defined standard, using the established templates, and checking that the document layout has been set by the author.
- To verify that referenced and annexed documents have been approved and released.
- To ensure the correct identification of documents.
- To store the electronic document native files (and on-line copies) of any final versions of documents in the document repository.
- To update documents with the appropriate signatures when approved.
- To send documents for review to reviewers, as defined in section 3.1.5.2
- To send documents for approval to the MUR. Documents are submitted to the MUR project portal and eventually sent by e-mail to the approval leader as identified in section 3.1.5.3.

3.1.5.2 Reviewer

Reviewers are peers of the author and have sufficient knowledge to assess the document's contents. The primary goal of a Reviewer is to detect and remove work document defects as early as possible in the development process. Secondary goals are:

- Ensure correctness, completeness, consistency, and accuracy of work documents for all life cycle activities within the development process.
- Educate WP/bodies staff and enhance their insight into WP/Bodies specific work documents and processes.
- Provide a technically-correct base for the next phase of development.
- Increase product quality.
- Achieve lower life-cycle cost.
- Provide a first indication of program maintainability.
- Increase WP productivity.
- Encourage entry/exit-criteria WP management.

3.1.5.3 Approver(s)

For the deliverables, the approval group is made up of PMO members, ITSERR Board members and the MUR officials in charge of the grant management. They may include individuals without executive responsibilities but with expertise in a specific domain (key users, technical experts, quality experts, etc.). If there are several Approvers, an Approval Coordinator is identified.

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MUR officials assign approval groups, their leaders and members.

Approval group members have the following responsibilities:

- To approve the documents submitted
- To give written and timely comments to the ITSERR Board, The Infrastructure Manager and the WP Leader.

The ITSERR Board and other ITSERR Approver(s) have the following responsibilities:

- To evaluate comments made by the MUR approval group members
- On this basis, to decide:
 - To approve accept the document(s) submitted for approval without comment.
 - To reject the document(s) submitted for approval, asking for corrections or modifications and for a new review process.

For documents that are not GA deliverables, any member of an advisory/management body or WP team can be an approver. Approvers have the following responsibilities:

- To approve the documents submitted
- To give written and timely comments to the body chairman or the WP Leader/PO.

3.1.5.4 Infrastructure Manager

The IM is responsible for establishing the proper Document Management follow-up and for guaranteeing the consistency of the document deliverables for MUR.

The Infrastructure Manager ensures that all the documents provided by the authors always meet the quality requirements of the MUR as client deliverables

3.1.6 Tasks

3.1.6.1 Prepare the document

What	A new document is prepared by the author.
Start	When a new document must be created
Roles involved	Document Author
Result	Document prepared The document receives the status "DRAFT"
Notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The author shall take care to ensure that: the document elaborated is strictly compliant with the document conventions (template, identification, version, structure, tools, writing rules, ...) and the document quality criteria, described more particularly in subsequent chapters. According to the process the document relates to, standards and guidelines recommended by the methodologies used must be followed.

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	<p>Any deviation to those rules and conventions must be documented</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The document is prepared with an approved computer application ○ Document conventions (header, trailer, date format ...) are followed
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3.1.6.2 Review the document

What	The author makes the document available to a group of reviewers, which must read the document, detect and remove work document defects. The group of reviewers must be composed of min. 3 people from min. 2 different institutions.
Start	When the document has been prepared
Roles involved	Reviewer(s)
Result	<p>List of remarks, requests for modifications and correction proposals to be brought to the document.</p> <p>The document receives the status "REVIEWED"</p>

3.1.6.3 Quality Review

What	<p>This is a formal quality check to reduce non-conformity of the document with conventions, standards, guidelines, and quality criteria, as well as to verify formal aspects of the document (identification, conventions, etc.). It also categorizes defects into two classes of severity: minor and major, with the following definitions:</p> <p>Minor: The defect makes the document difficult to read. There is a small possibility of wrong interpretation, and the defect could produce further defects in dependent documents or products.</p> <p>Major: The defect causes the possibility of misinterpretation in a larger part of the document (typically 2-3 pages) and will probably cause further defects in dependent documents or products. For this kind of defect, the Quality Reviewer returns the document to its author with the list of remarks and requested modification(s) and asks the author for a new review process.</p> <p>All documents that are part of the deliverables are subject to a formal quality review. However, to accelerate the process speed, this formal quality review may not be done for weekly meetings minutes, as far as the required quality level is met.</p>
Start	Before submitting the document to Approval group
Roles involved	Quality reviewer
Result	Document with comments, suggestion and correction verified

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	<p>In case the document is not conformant, defects are transmitted to the document author and corrections are brought to the document. In this case, the document status does not change.</p> <p>The document receives the status "VERIFIED"</p>
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3.1.6.4 Approve the document²

What	<p>In this process the document is reviewed by approval-group members. They forward their comments to the approval Leader, whose task is to collect and consolidate these comments within the agreed schedule. A review form or a specific collaborative tool with reviewing features shall be used to collect comments from the approval group members. Changes and comments are tracked directly in the document when possible.</p> <p>The document receives the status "UNDER APPROVAL".</p> <p>At the end of the time set for the approval, the approval group decides to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accept the document with no changes. • Accept the document with minor corrections. • Reject the document <p>The Approval Leader shall notify his decision by email to the Body chairman or the WP Leader (with copy to the author of the document).</p> <p>If the document is accepted the Approval Coordinator adds an approval signature in the Revision table, otherwise adds a review signature in the Revision table</p>
Start	Once the previous step is completed and at the time of the formal delivery of the documents ³ .
Parties Roles involved	<p>Approval Group</p> <p>Approval Coordinator</p>
Result	<p>Document accepted, accepted with corrections, or rejected.</p> <p>The Information about the status of this document is updated in the document logger with information needed to measure the process</p>

² In order to guarantee an acceptable schedule for any validation process inside this project, a period of 5 working days should be considered as a standard default value for the approval process. Longer or shorter periods may be defined depending on the length and complexity of the document submitted for approval, but must be agreed before between the approval leader and the approval requestor and must be clearly mentioned in the email requesting the approval.

³ All documents that are part of the GA deliverables are subject to a formal review and approval process before they are released for distribution to the MUR.

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	The document receives the status "APPROVED" or "REJECTED" according to the result of the approval cycle.
Notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To guarantee an acceptable schedule for any validation process inside this WP, a period of 5 working days should be considered as a standard default value for the approval process. Longer or shorter periods may be defined depending on the length and complexity of the document submitted for approval but must be agreed before between the approval leader and the approval requestor and must be clearly mentioned in the email requesting the approval. A maximum of two approval cycles should be considered as acceptable.

3.1.6.5 Correct the document⁴

What	Based on a list of remarks, requests for modifications and correction proposals, the author brings the necessary modifications to the document.
Start	When (quality) reviewers or approval group leader ask for modifications or corrections
Roles involved	Document Author
Result	Document reviewed and corrected, ready to be reviewed The document receives the status "DRAFT"

3.1.6.6 Release the document

What	The Author: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> completes the document with the necessary attributes (version number, approval date, approved by, status ...) uploads the document in the document repository. updates the document logger
Start	Once the document has been approved.
Roles involved	Author
Result	The document in DOCUMENT REPOSITORY The Information about the status of this document is updated in the document logger with all information needed to measure the process The document receives the status "FINAL"

⁴ A maximum of two approval cycles should be considered as acceptable.

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3.1.6.7 Deliver the document

What	The IM delivers the document to MUR by uploading the document onto the document repository. The IM informs the WP Leader or body chairman. ⁵
Start	The document has been verified and is ready to be delivered
Roles involved	IM
Result	Document-status information is updated in the document logger Document uploaded in the document repository and formally delivered for approval by MUR. The document receives the status "DELIVERED "

3.1.7 Outputs

Output of this process is the document updated/created and released onto the Document Repository into the specific folder.

3.1.8 Exit Criteria

The Document Management process exits when all steps have been completed and the approved document has been released onto the document repository.

3.1.9 Process Measures

The metrics to be collected for this process are:

3.1.9.1 Key Performance Indicator for the process

- Production and timely delivery of meeting agendas, reports, minutes
- Production and timely delivery of the MPR to the ITSERR Board by the Infrastructure Manager

3.1.9.2 Quality Indicators

All documents produced in the scope of the WP must comply with the following quality criteria.

Quality criterion	Description
Appropriate content for intended audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The document is clearly written with its audience in mind, their skills and job responsibilities. • The document's physical form is appropriate for the audience's work environment.
Availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The document is available to all readers at the agreed-upon time

⁵ Automatic notification must be used at every possible time

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Quality criterion	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A final delivery date has been defined before the document preparation, considering internal and external dependencies and resource availability
Cleanliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The document is legible on paper/screen The document is free of typographical, grammatical, and formatting errors
Completeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No needed information is missing.
Compliance with contractual requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The document complies with the standards and specifications included (or defined by reference) in the contractual requirements (whether Grant Agreement, specific contracts, or work statement)
Compliance with MUR document standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appropriate, recommended, or required documentation standards have been used. If templates or standards are not given for a special type of document, they must be created and agreed upon by MUR officials.
Consistency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The document does not contradict itself in either content or style. All terms have the same meaning throughout the document and within documents of which it forms a part. All items and concepts are referred to by the same name or description throughout the document, The level of detail and presentation style is the consistent throughout the document.
Correctness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The document contains no erroneous information.
Readability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of generally accepted rules of English grammar, capitalization, punctuation, symbols, and notation, Non-standard terms, phrases, acronyms, and abbreviations are defined, The information presented is logically organized, The level of complexity is appropriate to the intended audience, The information being presented can be interpreted in only one way

Table 3: Document Management Process – Quality Criteria

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3.1.10 Document Attributes

3.1.10.1 Document Reference

All documents are identified by a document reference that is structured to favour human readability and to simplify the process of searching and archiving.

The document reference has the following structure:

	Fixed part				Variable part		
	ITSERR	-	XX	-	XXX	YYYMMDD	(XX)
Part-Name	WP		Org. code		Document Type code	Event Code	Attachment Number
						Event Date	

Table 4: Document reference structure

Part-Name	Description and value	Value	Format
Organisational code	Code of the WP or body	e.g. WP1, PRC, IB	Uppercase characters
Document type code	Code identifying the type of the document itself or identifying the type of the main document if the document is an attachment	See Data Management Plan	3 uppercase characters (ie DOP for Detailed Organisational Plan)
Event code	Identification of the IT system concerned.	e.g. KICKOFF	Uppercase characters
Event Date	The meeting or event date. (only for recurrent documents)	Event date	YYYYMMDD
Attachments	Index of the attachment	For 01 to nn	2 digits into parenthesis

Table 5: Document reference description

3.1.10.2 Document version / revision number

New versions are created to reflect a major change or update to a document. The "Change History" table of the document should be updated to indicate a summary of the changes and/or reasons for the change.

The changes also must be formally reviewed and approved.

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New revisions of draft documents are created with the revision number 00.01, 00.02, 00.03 and so on. Upon the first final release of a document the revision number shall be updated to 01.00 and the status to "FINAL".

After any final release, the revision number shall be incremented whenever the document is changed in any way.

All documents with "FINAL" status must have the revision number equal to zero.

3.1.10.3 Document filename

The document filename must respect the following format:

	Document reference	-	XX	-	XX	.	doc xls pdf ..
Part-Name	Document reference		Version Number		Revision number		File extension

Table 6: Document filename structure

3.1.10.4

Part-Name	Description and value	Value	Format
Document reference	Reference of the document	see 3.1.10.1	see 3.1.10.1
Version	Version of the document		2 digits, starting with 00
Revision	Revision number		2 digits, starting with 00
Extension	Standard extension of the file	doc for Word xls for Excel pdf ...	3 characters

Table 7: Document filename description

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3.1.10.5 Document Status

3.1.10.6 Templates

Standard formats and templates have been established for all types of documents (meeting minutes, reports, etc.) and for most standard WP applications, such as Word and Excel.

The templates shall be made available to all authors.

3.1.10.7 Document Structure

The main characteristics of document design are outlined in the following sections. New document templates created for a WP or a body shall be prepared in compliance with the design described here.

3.1.10.8 Cover page

All documents must have a cover page which identifies the WP, the document, author, date of production, type of document, intended recipients, and quality-assurance information.

More precisely, each document must have a cover page containing:

- The MUR header or footer with the European flag,
- document title,
- author(s) of the document, accompanied with the company name into parentheses (ITSERR, MUR ...)
- document name as described in section
- version and the revision number of the document,
- date of the last revision,
- document status
- a revision table (change history) containing, for each revision:
 - revision number of the document itself,
 - revision date

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- object of the revision,
- status of the document (e.g. Draft),
- author(s) or approval leader name(s),
- identification of the verification or validation actions with names

3.1.10.9 Page header and footer

Moreover, on each page:

- document title and subject,
- document name,
- date of the last revision,
- status of the document
- page number / total pages,
- author (with company name)

3.1.10.10 Table of contents

Documents more than 3 pages long must be divided into chapters with each chapter structured into sections and sub-sections.

A contents page must be produced and included in the document after the cover page listing these chapters, sections and sub-sections. A consistent numbering scheme for chapters, sections and sub-sections must be used and chapters must be individually page-numbered (the page number must be chapter-page to facilitate document changes, so that individual chapters may be replaced without the need to reprint the entire document).

The documents more than 5 pages long must have a separate page with a table containing the chapters and sections with their page numbers.

3.1.10.11 Tables and Figures

Figures and tables must be included within the text rather than grouped at the end. They must be numbered consecutively, for example 'Figure 1', 'Figure 2' or 'Table 1', 'Table 2', and so on. Table headings must be placed above tables, with figure captions centred beneath figures.

3.1.10.12 Reference Information

If a document contains a lot of detailed reference information, it must contain a comprehensive index for easy reference.

When the tool allows it, references to other parts of the document must be dynamic, using cross-reference features.

3.1.10.13 Glossary

When a document is intended for a wide spectrum of readers, who may have differing vocabularies, it must clearly and briefly define its terms, expressions, and acronyms. The listed terms, expressions

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and acronyms must be sorted alphabetically. The glossary must be located at the end of the document, as the first appendix.

3.1.10.14 Document Properties

Whenever possible and to allow automated desktop processing, the documents must contain the following Summary properties:

- Title
- Subject (useful in case of documents broken into multiple parts)
- Author, accompanied of the company name (e.g., ITSERR, MUR)

As custom attributes, the following must also be included:

- Document ID
- Status
- Verified Reviewed by (reviewer(s))
- Verification Review date
- Validated Verified by (Infrastructure Manager)
- Validation Verification date
- Client Accepted by (approval leader)
- Client Acceptance Validation date

3.1.10.15 Date specification

To keep uniformity in all documents produced for this WP and to allow standardised searching by file-name pattern, the format used for the specification of a date should be as much as possible the following:

dd/mm/yyyy

3.1.11 File Management

3.1.11.1 Document classification

All documents are referenced in a document logbook. This logbook contains the following items for each document:

Field	Description
Document ID	Sequential unique number
Document Name	Refer to section 3.1.10
Current Status	Refer to section 3.1.10.5
Status Date	Date of status last change
Publ. date	Date of publication after approval.

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Author(s)	Names of authors.
Title	Title of the document.

Because the reference documents are living documents and so may be regularly updated, the referenced version is always the last final one and may be taken from the document logger.

3.1.11.2 Document types

The major document types are listed in the following table:

Type	Purpose
Monthly & Annual progress report	Report of the GA/WP status
Test report	Test log and result
Change request	Document that formalizes a user-need in a change request
Surveys	Questionnaires to monitor user satisfaction
GA, Amendments	Contractual documents from MUR and ITSERR
Minutes of the Meeting	Documents for record the participants, the decisions and actions taken in a meeting
Use Case/Story template	Used by WP6 to collect information on the behaviour/requirements of end-users upon data access
Various communications templates	Various templates are used to disseminate/communicate information within and without ITSERR
DOP	Detailed Operational Plan
QAP	This document

3.1.11.3 File types

Documents are made up of different elements: The main document, Annexes, and Attachments.

- The main document and its annexes are contained in a single electronic file.
- Annexes are referenced in the body and incorporated at the end of the main document.
- Attachments are self-supporting documents, referenced in the main document as "Related Documentation". They are separate electronic files, one for each attachment.
- Attachments must reference the main document and must in turn be referenced in the main document

3.1.11.4 File Handling

While a document is being prepared, the corresponding file(s) shall be stored in the working area of the author. This is normally the disk space of the workstation. The document is regularly stored in the Document Repository to simplify communication and sharing.

3.1.12 Document repository

All the information related to the technical solution, its set-up and follow-up are defined in the Data Management Plan See [AD3].

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3.1.13 Document Security

The need for document security varies according to the scale, sensitivity, and importance of the information and activities supported by the document. The security measures outlined below shall be followed

3.1.13.1 Confidentiality

The document author is responsible for setting the level of document confidentiality based on the following list of confidentiality levels:

- Confidential: restricted circulation, only for documents concerning contractual matters
- Public: no restrictions on circulation

3.1.13.2 Virus Control

Virus detection and prevention measures and appropriate user awareness procedures must be implemented for all documents.

3.2 Training Management

3.2.1 Purpose

The process entails the following activities:

- Training
 - Collection and analysis of training needs,
 - Courses Administration: absenteeism, syslog tool management, short-term and long-term planning
 - E-Learning tools and material
 - Training evaluation
 - Meeting rooms management
- Documentation and Communication
 - User manuals, online help
 - Hardware/Software guide
 - Newsletter
 - Web site update (newsletter, focus, who's who, videos, etc.)

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3.2.2 Process Diagram

Figure 3: Training and Coaching process diagram

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3.2.3 Roles and Responsibilities

3.2.3.1 Training Manager (TM)

The Training Manager is an experienced training leader that will start this activity from the materials provided by the ReIReS and RESILIENCE training services. S.he will analyse the training resources (people, procedures, skills, tools, etc.) necessary to create the ITSERR training framework allowing the later establishment of future training programmes, providing tools and methods to support researchers in using ITSERR services and/or even creating their own training materials

3.2.3.2 WP Leader/ Product Owner

The WP Leader (and/or the PO) is responsible for establishing that GA expectations in terms of training management are followed. The WP Leader (and/or the PO) assigns resources and tasking to the WP team organising the training, tracks effort expended and progress made. The WP Leader reports process progress to higher-level management.

3.2.3.3 WP Training team member

This group, composed of WP team members with skills in training creation, is responsible for executing the process. Each individual reports his/er progress through weekly metrics and makes recommendations for process improvement as the need arises to the WP Leader.

Each ITSERR partner delivering trainings provides the needed logistic such as the training room, computer and other materials.

3.2.3.4 Infrastructure Manager/ITSERR Board

Based on the GA objectives and the actual training plan, the IM/IB may request a new course/coaching to be documented and planned if relevant. The IM/IB also verifies that the objectives have been reached and that the training(d) performed as expected.

3.2.3.5 Trainee, Trainers

They receive/provide the training.

3.2.4 Entrance Criteria

A training need pops-up (Start Point 1) and a stakeholder provides a description of the training needed.

IM/IB can also require a course organisation (Start Point 1).

3.2.5 Inputs

The inputs of the process are:

- Existing learning material and ITSERR partners training offering,
- Training requirements at IM/IB level,
- Learning requests from ITSERR partners.

3.2.6 Tasks

The process described below covers the Training activity.

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3.2.6.1 Step A – New training need

What	When a training need is expressed by an internal/external ITSERR stakeholder		
Start	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirement message sent to a WP Training Team Request from an internal/external ITSERR stakeholder 		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team Trainees, Trainers Training Manager (TM) IM/IB 		
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of user training requirements subject to further investigation 		
Risk	Course does not exist	Preventive action(s)	Improve the course catalogue

3.2.6.2 Step 1 – Training Planning

What	<p>Planning is proposed on https://www.itserr.it/events/ website by the Training Manager covering various courses/schools.</p> <p>Based on this background and on the quantitative and qualitative assessment of the previous trainings, as well as on new needs expressed, WP Training Team proposes a series of courses.</p> <p>WP Training Team submits the courses schedule to the TM. Upon receipt of their informal agreement on the dates proposed, WP Training Team provides the TM with the final version of the planning, for it to formally start the courses. WP Training Team receives an agreement from TM about this planning.</p> <p>The TM updates the training catalogue on https://www.itserr.it/events/.</p>
Start	
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team organising the training TM
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the training material, service and catalogue

3.2.6.3 Step 2 – Communication material is provided

What	A WP Training Team member creates the communication material for the advertisement and registration for training
Start	When training is determined
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team

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Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the training material, service and catalogue Guidance to Trainee, Trainers applying for a course 		
Risk	User not familiar with web (newcomers)	Preventive action(s)	Better outline the importance of the registration tool in communication

3.2.6.4 Step 3 – Course exists?

What	To be able to register for a course, a course content must be created and approved.		
Start	When the training planning is defined/revised		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team 		
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> YES or NO 		

3.2.6.5 Step 4 – Course is created

What	The WP Training Team creates the draft course content and the training material.		
Start	When a training course is planned.		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team 		
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the training material, service and catalogue 		

3.2.6.6 Step 5 – Training content is verified and approved

What	The TM and the WP Leader/PO verify the draft course content and the training material before validating it and inserting it into training catalogue.		
Start	After draft course content is created.		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Leader/PO TM 		
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the training material, service and catalogue 		

3.2.6.7 Step 6 – Finalise inscriptions

What	<p>The TM checks each working morning to see whether new training enrolments have been validated. S/He verified in the course registry that the user has or has not been notified with the latest updates.</p> <p>For each training, this task takes place every day until the training date.</p>		
Start	When the training course is planned, possibly after step 5 and step B		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TM Trainee, Trainers 		

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Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainee, Trainers receives a meeting request in his mailbox to con/infirm his/her enrolment. • The TM gives the necessary follow up in case of rejection or tentative reply 		
Risk	No reply to the invitation	Preventive action(s)	Disseminate to Trainees, Trainers information about the availability of training. Proactive check on the status of applications by the TM, which decides to contact the Trainee, Trainers if appropriate.

3.2.6.8 Step 7 – Send reminder & last details

What	The user receives the necessary last notifications by email.		
Start	When the inscription is confirmed		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TM • Trainee, Trainers 		
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainee, Trainers receives a training information request in his/her mailbox. 		
Risk	Missing the training	Preventive action(s)	Disseminate to Trainees, Trainers latest information about the training.

3.2.6.9 Step B – User enrolment

What	The application for training is validated first by the TM		
Start	When the training course is planned, possibly after 2, 4 and 5		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainee, Trainers 		
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The TM has launched the invitation and is waiting inscriptions 		
Risk	Lack of time between enrolment and content validation by ITSERR staff	Preventive action(s)	Appointment of possible backups (at least at TM level) The TM gives attention to trainees' inscriptions not validated 2 weeks before the planned course

3.2.6.10 Step 8 – Training is given

What	An WP Training Team member gives the course him- or herself or asks another non-ITSERR trainers to do it.		
Start	When a training course has been planned.		

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Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team organising the training Trainee, Trainers
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve user knowledge, skills

3.2.6.11 Step 9 – Absenteeism management

What	WP Training Team member verifies the presence list and sends a standard mail to trainees who have not notified the team of their absence during the training.		
Start	At the end of the course		
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trainee, Trainers WP Training Team organising the training 		
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trainees, Trainers awareness 		
Risk	Possible withdrawal communicated by Trainee, Trainers but not recorded by WP Training Team organising the training	Preventive action(s)	Set up a systematic communication process between WP Training Team organising the training members

3.2.6.12 Step 10 – User evaluates the course.

What	Trainee, Trainers receives an e-mail with a link to complete the evaluation form.
Start	When the course has been given
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trainee, Trainers
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training is evaluated

3.2.6.13 Step 11 – Certificate of attendance is given

What	Trainers receives an e-mail with a link to complete the evaluation form.
Start	If the course has been followed-up completely (See section 3.2.6.11)
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trainee, Trainers
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A certificate of attendance is received by the trainee

3.2.6.14 Step 12 – Organiser evaluates the course.

What	Trainers and WP Training Team receives an e-mail with a link to complete the evaluation form.
Start	When the course has been given

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Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trainers and WP Training Team
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training is evaluated

3.2.6.15 Step 13 – Publishing Training material

What	Training material is published using the ITSERR.eu portal
Start	At the end of the course
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish information to improve the training material, service and catalogue

3.2.6.16 Step 14 – Update the Training quality report

What	<p>Twice a year, a report must be created and submitted to the IM/IB.</p> <p>This report presents a list of all courses given during the last 6 months and data encoded by the users, as well as a presentation of the possible problems in terms of attendance, evaluation and any other issue</p> <p>The report is used to analyse the problems and identify their causes.</p> <p>Based on this report, a document on service-quality improvement is written and included in the monthly report.</p> <p>This report is communicated to the IM/IB via the TM in the context of the Continuous Improvement.</p>
Start	6 months after the previous one
Roles involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP Training Team TM IM/IB
Result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the training material, service and catalogue

3.2.7 Outputs

Here is the list of the outputs:

- Training planning is created and made available in the ITSERR Training catalogue and published on ITSERR.eu
- Training is given;
- The evaluation of the training is performed by the trainees, trainers and the WP Training team;
- Training catalogue is kept up-to-date;
- The semestrally report on training improvement is produced and disseminated;

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3.2.8 Exit Criteria

The process can be closed once the training course has been evaluated by the user (End Point 1).

3.3 Continuous Improvement (CI) process

3.3.1 Purpose

The CI process is a comprehensive feedback process designed to assess WP outcomes and performance (both positive and negative). This assessment focuses on how well the WP outcomes were matched to the actual needs that the WP aimed to fulfil.

It also aims to collect and utilise knowledge learned and to identify ways in which the future of WPs can be improved.

The purpose of this section is to establish guidelines and procedures that define the objectives, activities and documentation required to perform a Continuous Improvement Review (CI).

3.3.2 Roles and Responsibilities

3.3.2.1 IM (IM)

The IM is responsible of the CI process. S/he reviews all information collected by the review group, s/he validates the CI report and provides feedback to the ITSERR Board.

3.3.2.2 ITSERR Board

The results of the Continuous Improvement Review are provided to the ITSERR Board, which will decide, given the findings of the CI report, on the actions to be performed (bring changes to the WP, adapt organization, change processes, incorporated lessons learned into future version of the QAP...).

3.3.2.3 Review group

The review group performs the review under the direction of the IM.

3.3.3 Tasks

This chapter identifies and describes the steps that shall be enacted to perform a CI.

3.3.3.1 Step 1 – Preparation

What	<p>Assessment of the needs and determination of CI goals and points of interest (special topic or area of the WP life-cycle that should be under scrutiny to assess the good/bad performance of the WP, i.e. test, performance, delays, quality measures, analysis ...).</p> <p>If necessary, the IM may appoint a contact person to perform the activities. This person shall belong to the WP team and s/he should have been significantly involved in the WP implementation</p>
Start	<p>It is part of the Steering Committee meeting (and the monthly report) or at the request of the IM or the ITSERR Board, if important quality issues have been identified (non-timely delivery, number of defects detected during the test phase too high, misalignment with end-users' expectations).</p>

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Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IM
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Goals and points of interest

3.3.3.2 Step 2 – Building the review group

What	<p>The IM, together with input from the PMO, identifies the participants that will conduct the review and attend the CI meeting. The objective of this step is to select few persons that, in accordance to the nature of the WP, were directly impacted by it. The selection can be done from all stakeholders (Board chairman, WP Leaders/POs, users, etc.)</p>
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IM PMO
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review group constituted

3.3.3.3 Step 3 – Collecting data and organizing review

What	<p>The PMO prepares a survey that addresses each point of interest defined at step 1 and send it to the review group. The PMO may also conduct interviews with key people of the review group or with external contributors (for example MUR, other academic institutions, ...) when necessary.</p> <p>The IM then compiles the answers and prepares a draft of the CI report, which highlights the major findings and issues provided by the review group through the survey and/or interviews.</p>
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PMO Review group
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CI survey Interviews (optional) Answers to the survey Draft of the CI report

3.3.3.4 Step 4 – CI meeting

What	<p>The PMO, together with the IM, arranges the CI meeting, establishing date and location.</p> <p>The PMO communicates final date and location of the meeting, together with any other information that is deemed to be important for the success of the meeting; the PMO ensures the presence of the participants and that they prepared in advance and bring relevant information.</p> <p>The agenda would cover the following points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> presentation of the major findings and issues, discussion of the WP for each point of interest, problems faced, solutions,
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lessons learned, • best practices, • summary (decisions, actions, risks)
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IM • PMO • Review group
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minutes of the meeting

3.3.3.5 Step 5 – Building CI report and providing feedback

What	<p>In addition to the minutes of the CI meeting, the PMO drafts the CI report and sends it for validation to the review group and the IM.</p> <p>The CI report will present the major points discussed at the meeting, problems, solutions, lessons learned, best practices and shall propose an action plan to implement solutions.</p> <p>The action plan as well as the lessons learned shall be documented in the next Monthly Progress Report in the relevant section.</p>
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IM • PMO • Review group
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CI report validated • Monthly Report updated

4 Risk Management

4.1 Overview

Consistent and active monitoring of risks and opportunities is essential for a successful rolling out of the MUR GA activities. The level of risk within the WP may be consistently contained and reduced by identifying risks and monitoring them regularly.

Risk management is considering as an integral part of the WP management process. To build a common risk and opportunities management framework within ITSERR and between ITSERR and MUR staff, the methodology described herein is applied. This methodology is a customization of the one described in the "European Commission - DG BUDG Risk Management Implementation Guide".

4.2 The proposed Risk Management Model

For a risk management strategy not to be solely reactive (actions put into place only when the risk occurs: implemented directly to manage emergencies), or if preventive, not just based on looking for the "most likely" risks, a real risk prevention strategy must be adopted.

The following image describes the approach adopted.

Figure 4: Summary of the Risk Management Process

This approach is compliant with the 5 key steps of the above-mentioned model adopted by the European Commission.

4.3 Risk Management Process

Following the above model, the next sections describe the steps that the IB, the IM, PMO, SO, WP Leaders and POs follow in handling risks.

4.3.1 Risks identification

The identification of risks is a systematic attempt to specify the threats to the WP planned activities. Risk identification must take into consideration the WP activities that will be influenced by any risk.

Once identified, all risks shall be listed in the Risk Register (see 4.3.3).

To better organize the risk identification, risks will be broken down as:

- **Internal Risks:** this category will include all risks that can rise as a direct consequence of actions taken within the Grant and involving ITSERR personnel or MUR personnel involved in the WP/service
- **External risks:** this category will include all risks that can rise as consequences of actions of external actors to the contract (e.g. third parties, hw or software vendors, etc) or of external events (e.g. strikes) or MUR or MUR personnel not involved in the performance of the current contract

Risks are categorized into the following groups:

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Type	Areas to consider when identifying potential risks
Costs	- Financial processes, - Effort estimation - Budget allocation
Deliverables	Quality and timeliness of deliverables
Performance	Performance indicators achievement
Personnel	- Human Resources (staffing, competences, collaboration) - Ethics and organisational behaviour (fraud, conflict of interests, etc.) - Internal ITSERR organisation
Technological	IT and other support systems
Administrative	- Clarity, adequacy and coherence of the ITSERR administrative processes with the applicable agreements, laws, regulations and rules.
Dissemination	- Communication methods and channels - Quality and timeliness of information
Process	Strategy, planning and policy decisions

Table 8: Categories of risk

4.3.2 Risks escalation procedure

The risks escalation procedure has four levels:

1. **WP level:** the risks are collected and recorded in the recurrent WP Team meeting proceedings, their ratings are agreed with the WP-L/PO, their mitigation is appropriately followed up;
2. **PM level:** the risks impacting one or several WPs with high Residual Risk level, after mitigation, are examined, eventually re-rated, solutions proposed, executed and followed up;
3. **ITSERR Board level:** the risks with a persistent Residual Risk level and likely to endanger the GA business are discussed and effective mitigation strategy is established;
4. **MUR level:** the risks with a Residual Risk level and likely to endanger the GA objectives is discussed and eventual contractual changes are established;

4.3.3 Risk Register

The Risk Register contains all risks identified. It should be limited to the most significant risks. The risk register is updated whenever there is a significant change in the GA's risk exposure, as a result of the risk management. For example, significant new risks may emerge during the year as a result of modifications in activities and objectives, re-organisations of management structures or systems, changes in the external working environment, etc. Also, significant new risks may be identified during the year via regular management and control activities, for example, by IB, IM, team leaders or ITSERR team members.

The Risk Register includes the following information.

<i>Risk ID</i>	Unique identifier of the risk with the GA
<i>Risk Title & Description</i>	The title and a detailed description of the risk(s)
<i>Probability</i>	The probability that a given event or issue will occur;

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<i>Impact</i>	The effect on the objectives/activities should the event or issue giving rise to the risk occur;
<i>Importance</i>	The importance of the risk related to the GA objectives
<i>Risk Category</i>	Risk typology
<i>Trigger Event/Indicator</i>	Event(s) that might allow to detect the risk occurrence or that will trigger the risk
<i>Risk Response & Description</i>	Verbose and generic statement regarding the response(s) to the risk
<i>Action Plan summary</i>	Identification of various potential risk responses (avoid, transfer, reduce, accept) for the highest priority risks
<i>Owner</i>	the person/entity in charge of the actions/measures to be taken;
<i>Status</i>	One of the following status: new, open, score unchanged, score increased, score decreased, ceased.
<i>Date Entered</i>	Date that the risk has been entered the risk register
<i>Date to Review</i>	Date when the next risk review will occur

Table 9: Risk record description

The Risk Register is available in the Document Repository (see 3.1.12). An extract of open risks is included into every Monthly Progress Report (see RD1).

4.3.4 Risk Assessment

Risk assessment is aimed at quantifying two major aspects: the probability (likelihood) that the risk will occur and the consequences (impact) of the resulting problems. These two evaluations are used to identify a severity score for each identified risk. This information is then reported within the risk register that will be the baseline for all ITSERR stakeholders' decisions regarding risks and opportunities.

For this Grant Agreement, ITSERR proposes to use the following evaluation criteria:

The Probability that an identified risk can occur, and the Impact of said risk will be evaluated using the following rating: 1-Very Low, 2-Low, 3-Medium, 4-High, 5-Very High.

The Risk rationale calculation includes the Probability rating and the Impact Rating, furnishing an integrated rating likely to drive the mitigation strategy; its calculation along with the Residual Risk calculation is based on the same scale applied to the Impact and Probability evaluation, giving a common rating framework, to allow the ratings comparisons.

Impact	Probability				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	2	3	4	5
2	2	4	6	8	10
3	3	6	9	12	15
4	4	8	12	16	20
5	5	10	15	20	25

Figure 5: Risk assessment matrix

Then the follow strategy is adopted based on the assessment.

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X	Unacceptable. Must treat and reduce risk via mitigation plan -> High Probability/High Impact
o	Undesirable. Must treat and reduce risk via mitigation plan -> Low Probability/High Impact & High Probability/Low Impact
√	Acceptable. Note and watch for possible escalation or aggregation. Normal activities of continuous improvement must still be applied -> Low Probability/Low Impact

4.3.5 Risk Mitigation

The Risk Register is complemented with a Risk Mitigation Register, encompassing the identified Mitigation actions for each Risk.

During the IB and Monthly progress meetings, the Mitigation actions are reviewed and if the implementation is completed and/or the related Risk is to be considered fully mitigated, the Risk Register is updated with the closure of the Risk in question while the Risk Mitigation Register is accordingly, simultaneously updated with the closure of the relevant Mitigation actions.

4.3.6 Risk Register

4.3.6.1.1 Grant Agreement

Here is the table from the ITSERR PNRR proposal.

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Actual costs exceed budgeted costs [Likelihood: Low][Severity:High]	Strict monitoring of costs with respect to progress Request extra inkind effort from partners Increase external co-funding
Delays in issuing project deliverables [Likelihood: Medium][Severity: Medium]	Adopt Agile methods for faster adaptability Implement early warning mechanism. Monthly progress review
Loss of digital data [Likelihood: Low][Severity: High]	Use fault-tolerant cloud services (ie CINECA) Store digital data in storages hosted in separate locations Sensitive data are subject to version control and back-up policy. Passwords to have access to key data are stored in secured shared password wallets.
Unavailability of personnel [Likelihood: High][Severity: Medium]	Identification of key personnel Each key person has a backup trained for cases of staff replacement
Physical gatherings not possible [Likelihood: High][Severity: Medium]	Replace physical attendances by videoconferencing Invest into digital/remote working paradigm hardware and software
Conflict among ITSERR partners	Escalation path through project entities to treat project issues

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[Likelihood: Medium][Severity: Low]

Implement measures of early warning.
Divert activities to partners able to implement them.
Pressure on partner (ie: costs transfers) if recurrent problems.

5 Quality Control System

To promote and ensure the highest level of quality in all services provided, ITSERR is putting in place a quality control system that will guarantee the minimum level of quality.

This quality system entails the following activities:

- Quality Control Definition
- Quality Control Implementation
- Quality Control Improvement

5.1 Quality Control Definition

This activity aims at defining methods, standards, organization of staff, quantitative measures, and quality control procedures necessary to control the quality of the services. This is included in the Quality Assessment Plan (this document).

5.1.1 Quality Criteria and Metrics

Following the analysis of the services to be provided, a set of quality criteria and quality metrics are defined for each process. These quality criteria and metrics are not intended to be used for the control of the service quality levels. This is the responsibility of the Performance Indicators Management process (see chapter 4). They quality criteria are described in sections specific to each process (see sections under chapter 2.2. above).

5.1.2 Standards and Methodologies

ITSERR will use the following standard methodologies throughout the Grant Agreement, for all phases of the WP:

- WP Management: PM² guidelines
- Performance Indicators Management: ITIL v3
- Quality Management: CMMI
- Design and Development: RUP, Agile, SCRUMM, UI/UX Ergonomics

5.2 External requirements

The following standards are to be applied for all documents and activities in the frame of the Grant Agreement.

- European Commission – Security Policy, Implementation Rules, Guidelines and Standards
- MUR constraints
- Code conventions

5.3 Quality Control Implementation

This part involves reviewing, inspecting, and auditing all the activities and deliverables to verify that they comply with the applicable procedures and standards, meet the quality criteria, and provide feedback regarding review and audit results.

5.3.1 Reviews

- **Records.** The meeting minutes of the WP are mainly used to verify that the quality program is being followed. If no records are readily available, audits may be used to identify deviations or weaknesses

In addition, the following techniques are applicable:

- **Workgroups.** On request of the ITSERR/MUR IM, workgroups may be used during the development effort; they are considered part of the quality verification process.
- **Formal reviews.** A formal review is held to obtain agreement and acceptance of deliverables.

The Infrastructure Manager does not usually conduct these reviews (but should at least have a controlling role): the process is much more valuable when team members and management do the reviewing and auditing.

5.3.2 Audits

Configuration audits have the purpose of ensuring the integrity of configuration items and are a prerequisite for the formal approval of the baseline of each single component.

The PMO, in accordance with the Software Development plan, performs the audits internally.

An audit will be performed before each contractual delivery to verify:

- the correct and complete identification of all the deliverables;
- the presence of the covering letter;
- the use of suitable packaging (e.g., organizing the various files of the delivery into a single file for transfer from development to deployment).

5.3.3 Surveys

The quality of on-going interactive work sessions, training sessions, and user support activities will be assessed through questionnaires that will be structured to permit quantitative analysis.

These surveys will be conducted in terms of the quality-control procedures and will be independent of regular surveys conducted in terms of the Performance Indicators Management. They will aim at assessing the overall quality of the services over longer periods of time. It is estimated that the quality-control surveys will be conducted twice a year.

5.3.4 Quality records

Quality records are retained to demonstrate the achievement of the required quality and the effective operation of the quality system.

5.4 Quality Control Improvement

ITSERR plans and performs internal audits on each service to ascertain its conformance level.

6 Service Level Management

Service Level Management is the on-going process of defining and managing the level of services required. The goal is to deliver cost-effective IT services of known quality.

In addition to the detailed description of all the procedures, organizational structure and tools (see sections above), the Service Level Management process will constantly monitor and report on the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which were part of the proposal.

6.1 Definitions

6.1.1 Feedback survey

The possible answers to the surveys that will be conducted to evaluate users/researchers' satisfaction are given in the table below. Surveys conducted in languages other than English will use the closest possible translation of these options.

The options given to the users to evaluate the quality is a score from 0(worst) to 10(best). A score superior or equal to 6 is considered POSITIVE.

6.1.2 Incident

An incident is any contact received in any form (e-mail, phone call or verbal communication from end users, the system, or third parties – IT Help desk, Data Centre, etc) and which gives information on an issue concerning the ITSERR Information Systems and/or requires any action (information, investigation, reporting, upgrade, etc).

Any problem that the services' staffs discover in production environments is also to be tracked via an incident.

Some of the incidents might, in specific cases, be excluded from the SLA timing on agreement with ITSERR. These incidents shall be marked as being excluded from the SLA by that person, clearly identifying which of the intervention, resolution, and final correction times are excluded and why.

The following table shows the classification of urgency given to the incidents. The type of incident and the user population impacted determine the priority (urgency).

Issue / Population impacted	System Down ⁶	Blocking Problem ⁷	Security issue	Data anomaly or incoherence	Non-Blocking Problem	All other issues ⁸
The whole DG	Very Urgent	Very Urgent	Very Urgent	Very Urgent	Very Urgent	Urgent
Single Unit	Very Urgent	Very Urgent	Very Urgent	Urgent	Normal	Low

⁶ One or more layers are not available (e.g., RDBMS, Application Server, interfaces with external systems etc.)

⁷ A main functionality does not work in production and the users cannot complete their work correctly and there is not a possible workaround (most likely one or more defects must be open if the problem is not caused by the infrastructure).

⁸ Typically, information and support to users

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Individual	Urgent	Urgent	Very Urgent	Normal	Low	Low
Individual VIP	Very Urgent	Urgent				

Table 10: Incident classification

6.1.3 Incident Management

Incident classification is initially done by the DCS Central Helpdesk and may be reviewed and approved by a PMO and/or IT-team member, who can also downgrade or upgrade the classification.

All incident steps have to be recorded, at the time of status transition, and followed up in incident-management software that allows the intervention and resolution times to be monitored. An incident may be closed only upon approval by the incident issuer or upon Commission overrule.

The minimum service level for incident management is monitored by measuring the time each incident remains in a given status. The target minimum service level for each type of incident is given in the following table.

Incident Priority	Acknowledgement Time	Intervention Time (starting from the time of the request)	Resolution Time
1 - Critical	< 10 minutes	< 2 hours	< 4 hours
2 – High	< 10 minutes	< 4 hours	< 8 hours
3 - Moderate	< 30 minutes	< 6 days	< 1 week
4 - Low	< 30 minutes	< 1 month	< 1 month

Table 11: SLA Targets for incidents⁹

When an incident exceeds its resolution threshold, a specific warning procedure has to be started in order to inform the PMO. Incidents rated "Very Urgent" as well as incidents related to security or confidentiality issues will always be reported without any delay.

An incident that gives rise to a problem can be closed while the problem remains open only where a workaround was provided and accepted by the user or incident issuer.

6.1.4 Time measurement

For the purpose of verifying compliance with the Service Level Agreement, days indicated in this document are calculated as "working days" unless otherwise specified. Therefore, if a problem that has a target resolution time of 5 days is opened on a Friday, the target resolution date is one calendar week later (on the next Friday at the same hour).

The same is true when time is measured using hours. Only "working hours" will be considered for the purpose of calculating the time that has elapsed. If the "working hours" for a specific service are

⁹ Times are calculated in working days and hours.

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8:30-18:30, a call with a target resolution time of 8 hours starting at 14:30 will have a target resolution date of 12:30 the next working day.

6.2 Service Level Agreement

The Service Level Agreement (SLA) defines, in terms of performance and quality targets, the minimum service level required for each service provided.

6.2.1 Key Performance Indicators

The minimum level of service will be assessed according to the measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined below.

The following table defines the key performance indicators and service-level targets for all the services. A certain degree of flexibility is possible on a case-by-case basis, and only with the prior explicit agreement of ITSERR IB. KPIs are monitored per calendar month unless stated otherwise.

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Proposal ID	DOP ID	Type	Title	Accountable	Responsible	Measurement Starts on	Measurement done by	Measurement periodicity
KPI1.1	KPI1.1	Incident Management	Incident acknowledgement time	PMO	IT Lead	As soon as OPER is available		Monthly
KPI1.15	KPI1.10	Progress Report	Compliance with the delivery date of the bi-monthly progress report	IM	PMO, SO	01/11/2022		Bi-monthly
KPI1.16	KPI1.11	Progress Report	Compliance with the expected content of the bi-monthly progress report	IM	PMO, SO	02/11/2022		Bi-monthly
KPI1.17	KPI1.12	Progress Report	Quality of the Financial report (including invoicing, evidences, etc.) submitted to the Ministry	IM	PMO, SO	03/11/2022		Bi-monthly
KPI1.2	KPI1.2	Incident Management	Incident intervention time	PMO	IT Lead	As soon as OPER is available		Monthly
KPI1.3	KPI1.3	Incident Management	Incident Resolution time	PMO	IT Lead	As soon as OPER is available		Monthly
KPI1.4	KPI1.4	IT Software Development Life Cycle Efficacy	Number of release rolled back	PMO	IT Lead	As soon as First release on PROD environment		Monthly
KPI1.5	KPI1.5	IT Software Development Life Cycle Efficacy	Number of defects in release/change in PRD - Incidents caused by new releases	PMO	IT Lead	As soon as First release on PROD environment		Monthly
KPI1.6	KPI1.6	IT Software Development Life Cycle Efficacy	Defects not found during test execution in non-PRODUCTION	PMO	IT Lead	As soon as First release on PROD environment		Monthly
KPI1.7	KPI1.7	IT Software Development Life Cycle Efficacy	Test execution coverage	PMO	IT Lead	As soon as First release on PROD environment		Monthly
KPI1.13	KPI1.8	Configuration Management DB	Implementation of updates to Configuration Management DataBase (CMDDB) arising out of change management process	PMO	IT Lead	Start of the IT services contract		Monthly

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KPI1.14	KPI1.9	Knowledge Management	Number of Knowledge Management (KM) artefacts with an expired review date	PMO	IT Lead	Start of the IT services contract		Monthly
KPI10.0a	KPI10.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI10.0b	KPI10.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI10.1	KPI10.3	WP Product Efficiency	Feedback on the Preliminary data model	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI10.2	KPI10.4	WP Product Efficiency	Feedback on the Preliminary data model	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI10.3	KPI10.5	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on Annotation tools and interactive interface				M12, M24, M26	3 times
KPI10.4	KPI10.6	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on Annotation tools and interactive interface				M12, M24, M26	3 times
KPI10.5	KPI10.7	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on ReTINA	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M30	
KPI10.6	KPI10.8	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on ReTINA	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M30	
KPI11.1	KPI11.1	TNA Service	Per each TNA, Level of scientific relevance is measured by the percentage of the scientific Peer Review Committee (PRC) that analysed the proposals	SC	WP-L	After the 1st TNA call has been closed		
KPI11.2	KPI11.2	TNA Service	Access provision Efficiency	SC	WP-L	After the 1st TNA call has been closed		
KPI11.3	KPI11.3	TNA Service	TNA Efficiency	SC	WP-L	After the 1st TNA call has been closed		
KPI11.4	KPI11.4	TNA Service	Access Quality	SC	WP-L	After the 1st TNA call has been closed		

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KPI11.5	KPI11.5	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		
KPI11.6	KPI11.6	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with agreed planned activities	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		
KPI11.7	KPI11.7	Knowledge Management	Number of Knowledge Management (KM) artefacts with an expired review date	SC	WP-L	After the 1st TNA call has been closed		Monthly
KPI12.1	KPI12.1	Data Management Quality	Number of Master Data Model release back-outs	PMO	WP-L	After the 1st release		Monthly
KPI12.2	KPI12.2	Data Management Quality	Data test execution coverage	PMO	WP-L	After the 1st testing of the DMS		Monthly
KPI12.3	KPI12.3	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI12.4	KPI12.4	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with agreed planned activities	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI12.5	KPI12.5	Project and Quality Management	Delay in successful implementation of corrective action plan following quality audits	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI12.6	KPI12.6	Project and Quality Management	# incident report due to quality issues with a deliverables	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI12.7	KPI12.7	Configuration Management DB	Implementation of updates to Configuration Management DataBase (CMDB) arising out of change management process	PMO	IT Lead	Start of the IT services contract		
KPI12.8	KPI12.8	Knowledge Management	Number of Knowledge Management (KM) artefacts with an expired review date	PMO	IT Lead	Start of the IT services contract		Monthly
KPI2.0	KPI2.1	Incident Management	Incident acknowledgement time	PMO	WP-L	As soon as OPER is available		Monthly
KPI2.9	KPI2.10	DCS operations	Quantity of incidents not solved within the time frame foreseen by the service level	PMO	WP-L	Start of the DCS in the DEV, TEST		Monthly

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						or PROD environment		
KPI2.10	KPI2.11	DCS operations	Quantity of system maintenance operations not performed by the DCS team (i.e. security patching, etc.)	PMO	WP-L	Start of the DCS in the DEV, TEST or PROD environment		Monthly
KPI2.11	KPI2.12	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI2.12	KPI2.13	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI2.13	KPI2.14	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with agreed planned activities	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI2.14	KPI2.15	DCS operations	Delay in successful implementation of corrective action plan following quality audits	PMO	WP-L	As soon as First release on PROD environment		Monthly
KPI2.15	KPI2.16	DCS operations	# incident report due to quality issues with a deliverables	PMO	WP-L	As soon as First release on PROD environment		Monthly
KPI2.16	KPI2.17	DCS operations	Service Desk reachability through communication channels during working hours	PMO	WP-L	As soon as First release on PROD environment		Monthly
KPI2.1	KPI2.2	Incident Management	Incident intervention time	PMO	WP-L	As soon as OPER is available		Monthly
KPI2.2	KPI2.3	Incident Management	Incident Resolution time	PMO	WP-L	As soon as OPER is available		Monthly
KPI2.3	KPI2.4	DCS operations	System/service availability	PMO	WP-L	As soon as DEV is available		Monthly
KPI2.4	KPI2.5	DCS operations	System/service availability	PMO	WP-L	As soon as TEST is available		Monthly
KPI2.5	KPI2.6	DCS operations	System/service availability	PMO	WP-L	As soon as OPER is available		Monthly

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KPI2.6	KPI2.7	DCS operations	Quantity of incidents due to capacity (CPU, Memory, storage)shortages	PMO	WP-L	Start of the DCS in the DEV, TEST or PROD environment		Monthly
KPI2.7	KPI2.8	DCS operations	Quantity of incidents having impacted the security of the ITSERR environments	PMO	WP-L	Start of the DCS in the DEV, TEST or PROD environment		Monthly
KPI2.8	KPI2.9	DCS operations	Quantity of incidents having impacted the backup of the ITSERR environments	PMO	WP-L	Start of the DCS in the DEV, TEST or PROD environment		Monthly
KPI3.0a	KPI3.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI3.9	KPI3.10	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback from GNORM prototype testers				M18, M24, M26	3 times
KPI3.0b	KPI3.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI3.1	KPI3.3	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on CRITERION prototype testers				M16, M22, M26	3 times
KPI3.2	KPI3.4	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on CRITERION prototype testers				M16, M22, M26	3 times
KPI3.4	KPI3.5	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the data mining algorithm	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M20	Once
KPI3.5	KPI3.6	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the data mining algorithm	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M20	Once
KPI3.6	KPI3.7	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of automatic properties annotation system	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M24	Once
KPI3.7	KPI3.8	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of automatic properties annotation system	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M24	Once
KPI3.8	KPI3.9	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback from GNORM prototype testers				M18, M24, M26	3 times

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KPI4.0a	KPI4.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI4.7	KPI4.10	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on DaMSym platform	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M16, M22, M24	
KPI4.0b	KPI4.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI4.1	KPI4.3	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of word embedding extraction tool for DaMSym	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M12	Once
KPI4.2	KPI4.4	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of word embedding extraction tool for DaMSym	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M12	Once
KPI4.3	KPI4.5	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the machine translation tool for DaMSym	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI4.4	KPI4.6	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the machine translation tool for DaMSym	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI4.5	KPI4.7	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the text classification and document understanding tool for DaMSym	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M20	Once
KPI4.6	KPI4.8	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the text classification and document understanding tool for DaMSym	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M20	Once
KPI4.7	KPI4.9	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on DaMSym platform	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M16, M22, M24	
KPI5.0a	KPI5.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI5.0b	KPI5.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI5.1	KPI5.3	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of algorithm for automatic text recognition	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M16	Once
KPI5.2	KPI5.4	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of algorithm for automatic text recognition	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M16	Once

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KPI5.3	KPI5.5	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of algorithm for metadata extraction	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M16	Once
KPI5.4	KPI5.6	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of algorithm for metadata extraction	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M16	Once
KPI5.5	KPI5.7	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of intelligent and automated cataloguing prototype				M20, M24, M28	3 times
KPI5.6	KPI5.8	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of intelligent and automated cataloguing prototype				M20, M24, M28	3 times
KPI6.0a	KPI6.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI6.0b	KPI6.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI6.1	KPI6.3	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for automatic metadata extraction on visual and audiovisual data				M12, M18, M26	3 times
KPI6.2	KPI6.4	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for automatic metadata extraction on visual and audiovisual data				M12, M18, M26	3 times
KPI6.3	KPI6.5	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for layout analysis to automatically extract texts and images				M12, M18, M26	3 times
KPI6.4	KPI6.6	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for layout analysis to automatically extract texts and images				M12, M18, M26	3 times
KPI6.5	KPI6.7	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on YASMINE applied to Sanctuaria	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M28	
KPI6.6	KPI6.8	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on YASMINE applied to Sanctuaria	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M28	
KPI7.0a	KPI7.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI7.8	KPI7.10	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on REVER (user interface + algorithms)	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M14, M22, M28	

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KPI7.0b	KPI7.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI7.1	KPI7.3	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of HTR/OCR tool	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M14	Once
KPI7.2	KPI7.4	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of HTR/OCR tool	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M14	Once
KPI7.3	KPI7.5	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for linking regesta to their sources	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI7.4	KPI7.6	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for linking regesta to their sources	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI7.5	KPI7.7	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for automatically producing regesta from sources	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M24	Once
KPI7.6	KPI7.8	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for automatically producing regesta from sources	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M24	Once
KPI7.7	KPI7.9	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on REVER (user interface + algorithms)	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M14, M22, M28	
KPI8.0a	KPI8.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI8.8	KPI8.10	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on uBIQUity deployed (based on the analysis conducted)	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M16, M22, M30	
KPI8.0b	KPI8.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI8.1	KPI8.3	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for finding Biblical and Qranic quotations in the respective corpora of commentaries	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI8.2	KPI8.4	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for finding Biblical and Qranic quotations in the respective corpora of commentaries	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M18	Once
KPI8.3	KPI8.5	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for finding Biblical and Qranic quotations in the respective corpora of commentaries	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M20	Once

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KPI8.4	KPI8.6	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for finding Biblical and Qranic quotations in the respective corpora of commentaries	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M20	Once
KPI8.5	KPI8.7	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for suggesting Biblical and Qranic allusions in the respective corpora of commentaries	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M22	Once
KPI8.6	KPI8.8	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the algorithm for suggesting Biblical and Qranic allusions in the respective corpora of commentaries	WP-L, PO	IT-L		M22	Once
KPI8.7	KPI8.9	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on uBIQUity deployed (based on the analysis conducted)	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M16, M22, M30	
KPI9.0a	KPI9.1	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with delivery dates agreed in the Deliverable Tracking Matrix (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI9.8	KPI9.10	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on the TAURUS toolkit (EnLil, MiRAR and ACIS)	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M30	
KPI9.0b	KPI9.2	Project and Quality Management	Compliance with the expected content of the deliverables as agreed in the (DTM)	PMO	WP-L,PO	01/11/2022		Monthly
KPI9.1	KPI9.3	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the EnLil prototype				M12, M22, M24	3 times
KPI9.2	KPI9.4	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the EnLil prototype				M12, M22, M24	3 times
KPI9.3	KPI9.5	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the MiRAR prototype				M12, M22, M24	3 times
KPI9.4	KPI9.6	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the MiRAR prototype				M12, M22, M24	3 times
KPI9.5	KPI9.7	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the ACIS prototype				M12, M22, M24	3 times
KPI9.6	KPI9.8	WP Product Efficiency	Efficiency of the EnLil prototype				M12, M22, M24	3 times

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KPI9.7	KPI9.9	Researchers' quality feedback	Feedback on the TAURUS toolkit (EnLil, MiRAR and ACIS)	WP-L	PO, IT-L		M30	
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Table 12: Service Level targets and indicators

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6.2.2 SLA Monitoring

The PMO shall enforce this SLA for all services provided.

This section describes how the SLA will be enforced and monitored during the GA execution.

Figure 6: SLA Monitoring

6.2.2.1 SLA Report Preparation

Periodically, PMO produces a report on the execution of the SLA. This report is included into the monthly progress report, whether it is monthly and it also highlights the most important KPI deviations and propose an action plan for implementing improvements.

The major sources of information are:

- Contact management tool
- Change Management tool
- Other sources of information

The following tasks are performed:

- Step 1 – Choose the period

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What	The PMO chooses the period (monthly, annual). All needed information is extracted from Contact management tool, Change Management tool and other appropriate sources of information.
Start	once a month for monthly report, once a year for annual report
Roles involved	PMO
Result	Necessary information extracted for report creation

- Step 2 – Extract data and build the dashboard

What	The report shows all KPIs and values for the period. The focus is placed on the elements that do not respect the SLAs.
Start	At the end of step 1
Roles involved	PMO
Result	Dashboard

- Step 3 – Include into the next progress report

What	The PMO uploads the dashboard onto the document repository and includes it into the next progress report (MPR or APR).
Start	At the end of step 2
Roles involved	PMO
Result	"Service Level Management" section updated into the MPR/APR

6.2.2.2 SLA Monitoring

This activity refers to the continuous monitoring of the service level to verify compliance with the specified requirements, time, and quality targets.

PMO continuously manages the levels of service by defining and enforcing:

- Continuous monitoring of KPI (see below)
- Mechanisms for the effective and efficient handling of change requests
- continuous evaluation of potential risks and mitigation measures (see risk management process)
- a well-defined security framework that ensures the overall security of the systems and of supported applications
- an effective and efficient strategy for exchanging information among the roles involved

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- effective planning and management of human resources in a way that guarantees service availability even in cases of increased workload or unexpected unavailability of personnel

6.2.2.3 KPI monitoring process

This process describes how the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) are monitored. The process entails a periodic review meeting, normally every month at the time of the Steering Committee meeting, to discuss service level and all metrics (KPI and quality indicators) and whether they are conforming to the targets and objectives. If not, determine the root cause of the problems, propose solutions to meet or exceed the service level and quality requirements and implement improvements.

Current initiatives and progress in improving individual situations are also covered during this review meeting.

The roles and responsibilities are:

- PMO: The PMO monitors and reports on KPIs.
- ITSERR IM.

The input for the process is the KPI measurements for the period covered (usually one month) for all services, as part of the Monthly Progress Report.

The following tasks must be performed:

- Step 1 – Identify all KPI deviations

What	The IM makes the list of all deviations of the KPI values against the targets set in the SLA (for the period covered)
Start	Every month, at the time of the production of the Monthly Progress Report.
Roles	IM
Results	List of KPI deviations in the Monthly Progress Report (in Service Level Management section)

- Step 2 –Root causes analysis of the deviations

What	The IM identifies the root causes of deviations based on a thorough analysis of the current and past values, and plan specific initiatives to address them. KPI improvement initiatives should focus on strengthening business fundamentals without losing sight of cost efficiency and responsiveness.
Start	Every month, each time a KPI deviation is identified.
Roles	IM
Results	List of root causes of gap in service level performance in the Monthly progress Report (in Service Level management section)

- Step 3 – Define and follow-up Service Level improvement actions

What	Based on the root causes analysis, the IM defines and plans a series of Service Level improvements actions to address the major causes and
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	correct the deviations. Service Level Improvement action plan should focus on strengthening quality and service level without losing sight of cost efficiency and responsiveness of the actions.
Start	For each root cause identified.
Roles	IM PMO
Results	<p>Service Level improvement action plan (description of the action, deadline, status ...)</p> <p>The action plan must form part of the Monthly Progress Report (Service Level Management section)</p> <p>The action plan is discussed and agreed upon during the Steering Committee meeting</p> <p>The Service Level improvement actions must be implemented and followed-up according to the agreed plan.</p>

- Step 4 –Service Level Management review (on request)

What	<p>Service level management reviews in a monthly meeting with persons responsible for measuring and providing defined service levels (PMO and IM). The purpose of the meeting is to review performance of the measured service level (KPI) and improvement actions follow-up.</p> <p>Each meeting should have a defined agenda that includes a review of measured service levels for the given period, a review of improvement initiatives defined, current service level metrics.</p> <p>A discussion of what improvements are needed based on the current set of metrics.</p>
Start	On request of the IM.
Roles	IM PMO
Results	Meeting minutes

The main results of the process are:

- The list of KPI deviations for the period covered
- The list of root causes

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7 Control of the QAP

7.1 Preparation

QAP should be delivered for acceptance to the ITSERR Board.

7.2 Follow-up Activities

The QAP is a living document which is updated at least yearly to take account of new information and changed requirements, and whenever it is required by MUR.

This update follows the same MUR acceptance process than the initial version.

The ITSERR Infrastructure Manager is in charge to revise and update the QAP as appropriate.

7.3 Lack of Adherence to the QAP

The ITSERR Infrastructure Manager is responsible for the follow-up of the QAP prescriptions during the whole WP.

An explicit review of the QAP as well as a measurement of the adherence will be done at least yearly, and the detected deviations and/or potential enhancements will be reported to the ITSERR IM who will assure that all corrective actions are taken.

8 Annex 1 - Glossary

Term	Definition
Baseline	A significant state within the history of any planned activity
Best Practice	Proven Activities or Processes that have been successfully used by multiple Organisations.
Blocking problem	A problem for which no workaround solution is available at the time of the discovery and which prevents the normal use of the product or of a main functionality
Change management	The process responsible of controlling and tracking changes to deliverables.
Change Request (CR)	A general term for any request from a stakeholder to change an artefact or process. A change request can be an Enhancement Requests or a Defect
MUR	Direction Générale de la Recherche
Escalation	Process that pass information and/or requesting action on an incident, problem or change to more senior staff (hierarchical escalation)

Grant Agreement	Contract signed between the Commission and the ITSERR consortium for the provision of research activities for the creation of a community and research infrastructure on religious studies
Incident	An unplanned interruption to a service or a reduction in the quality of a Service.
Information System	A system, whether automated or manual, that comprises people, machines, and/or methods organised to collect, process, transmit, and disseminate data that represent intermediate or final outputs of business processes.
Performance Indicator (PI)	A Metric that is used to help manage a Process, Service or Activity. Many Metrics may be measured, but only the most important of these are defined as PIs and used to actively manage and report on the Process, Service or Activity. PIs should be selected to ensure that Efficiency, Effectiveness, and Cost Effectiveness are all controlled.
Monthly Progress Report (MPR)	Report provided every month containing all necessary information to follow-up the Grant execution
Performance Level Agreement (PLA)	Agreement between ITSERR and the Commission specifying, in measurable terms, the levels of performance to be provided to the Commission.
Continuous Improvement Review (CI)	CI is a comprehensive feedback process designed to assess WP outcomes and performance. This assessment focuses on how well the WP outcomes were matched to the actual needs that the WP aimed to fulfil.
Process	Sequence of activities designed to accomplish a specific objective. A Process takes one or more defined inputs and turns them into defined outputs. A Process defines roles, responsibilities, tasks, tools, standards and management controls required.
Repository	A storage place for work products (artefacts) output during process enactment, such as requirements, results (i.e. metrics), object models, interfaces, and implementations.
Review	Activity carried out to discover potential defects and to assess the quality of a set of artefacts.
Risk	A possible Event that could cause harm or loss or affect the ability to achieve Objectives. A Risk is measured by the probability of a Threat, the Vulnerability of the Asset to that Threat, and the Impact it would have if it occurred.
Risk Management	The Process responsible for identifying, assessing and controlling Risks.

Service	A means of delivering value to Customers by creating Outcomes Customers want to achieve without the ownership of specific Costs and Risks.
Work Package (WP)	Agreement between the MUR and ITSERR to perform a set of activities grouper under a common topic or theme. Each WP has a set of activities under a defined schedule and with defined deliverables, effort, and resource constraints.
WP leader	The WP leader is the interface between the IB and WP team members. The WP leader is responsible for ensuring that a task is allocated and monitored to completion. The WP leader is responsible for ensuring that staff follow WP standards, and adhere to WP schedules.

9 Annex 2. List of ITSERR Project/Contract Management Templates

The list of document types, with their associated document codes and templates is presented in the table below. The document templates are available into the template repository folder under 3. Useful Materials & Food4Thought.

Document without a specific template shall use the following generic template: ITSERR-doc-vo.1.dot

Document Type	Process or phase concerned	Document code	Template filename
Minutes of ad-hoc Meetings	Document Management	MAM	ITSERR-TMPL-MAM.dot
Minutes of Steering Committees Meetings	Management	MMM	ITSERR-TMPL-MMM.dot
Minutes of Weekly Meetings	Management	WMM	ITSERR-TMPL-WMM.dot
Monthly Progress report	Document Management	MRP	ITSERR-TMPL-MPR.dot

10 Annex 3. List of ITSERR Project/Contract Management Dashboards

The list of dashboards, with their associated document codes and templates is presented in the table below.

Dashboard	Description	Document code	Location
KPI Dashboard	Dashboard aimed at performing the monthly management of the KPI	XLS	PMO folder
Financial reporting (XLS)	Dashboard aimed at performing the financial management of the contract	XLS	Support Office folder
Human Resource Management (XLS)	Dashboard aimed at performing the monthly management of the KPI	XLS	PMO folder

(End of Document)